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Research Article

**PREVALANCE OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT BLOOD DONATION
AND TRANSFUSION IN PAKISTANI POPULATION**¹Dr. Adil Majeed, ²Dr. Ghalia Asrar, ³Dr. Fawad ul haq¹Medical Officer, BHU Verum Chak 4, Chunian, Kasur²Woman Medical Officer, THQ Pattoki, Kasur³District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital Dera Ismail khan**Abstract:**

Objectives: Giving blood to help others and transfer of donated blood to other human beings are safe methods. But awareness, faiths and stances of the people linked with these two medical terms and can affect the safety of procedures. The aim of this research was to describe the awareness faiths and stances about giving and transferring of blood in the people of Pakistan.

Methodology: This research work conducted at Mayo Hospital Lahore. Questions in Urdu language were in use to check the faiths, behaviour and awareness for giving and transferring of blood in Pakistani population.

Results: Three hundred and thirty-five men and two hundred and seventy-four women were the participants of this study. More than sixty-five percent participants never donated blood. About eighty percent of non-donors were from fifteen years to thirty year of age. There was a belief in more than eighty-eight percent participants that donation of the blood to the human being is not an unhealthy activity. Twenty percent participants had the view that they would reject the transferring of the blood or plasma if they were in a condition of danger because it would bring complicated diseases to them from other persons. There were some participants who believed that they would receive blood only from their relatives. They were forty-nine percent.

Conclusion: The mistaken belief about the donation of the blood and its transfusion should be tackled by the education, ending up the false ideas about the hospitals and ignorance. This will motivate the donors to perform the noble deed. People should be aware of several preventive measures that handle the donation of blood and transferring of blood in the recipient.

Keywords: faith, ignorance, behaviour, stance, donor, recipient, transfusion, donation

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INTRODUCTION:

Different research works cannot pass in searching out a complete in lieu of the blood and its main components as RBC, WBC, serum and platelets etc [1]. So, for the completion of the need of blood components and blood, the donation of the blood will continue forever by human beings. There are many occasions in which persons can loss their large amount of blood such as wars between countries, during surgeries, in serious accidents and there are some diseases which directly involve the blood as anaemia in which red blood cells are in low quantity and an individual feels tired or low platelet quantity in the blood. So, blood donation is a very noble act and saver of the human life. It is the responsibility of the blood stores to give the proper blood group and clear supply to the populations. The ratio between donors and recipients always fluctuates and does not remain on equilibrium condition. There are several types of donation as on payment donation, willing donation and direct donation. These donations are the way of getting the blood and its important ingredients. The willing donors should be examined carefully before obtaining blood. Direct donors are the relative or close family friends from whom blood transferring carried out to specific recipient [2, 3]. On payment donation performed with the exchange of cash [4]. In autologous donation, the donor and the recipient is the same person. Blood storage carried out in safe condition and then transfused to same person at the time of surgery [5-10]. Ignorance faiths and the stances are the things which can motivate or depress the donors of blood.

The process of transferring blood and its ingredients varies from department to department. This process depends upon the service provided by the LAB and quantity of the sufferers available [3]. According to the need of the recipients' blood plasma or blood ingredients transfused to the sufferers. It is common belief that transfusion of blood is a dangerous act

[13], although many preventive steps have been taken in the same field to prevent the infections [14, 15]. This research provides us with the faith and knowledge of Pakistani community about donation of blood and transfer of blood from one person to another. The outcome of this study will end up the misconception arising about blood transfusion and blood donation.

METHODOLOGY:

This research carried out in Mayo Hospital Lahore from 2017 to 2018. Good ordered questions in Urdu language were in use to check the faith, ideas, behaviour, stances and awareness about the processes of blood transfer from one person to another person and donation of blood in six hundred and nine participants of Pakistan. The social and economic data collected from question answer session. Three hundred and thirty-five males and two hundred and seventy-four females from fifteen years to sixty-five years of age were the participants of this research. This age is the prerequisite for the donation of blood. The purpose of study introduced to the participants. Social science version twelve SSV was in use for data entry.

RESULTS:

The outcome collected from six hundred and nine participants. In this research, fifty-five percent were males and forty-five percent were the female participants. Sixty-five point eighty-four percent participants were not donors. The non blood donors gave some reasons of not donating blood as they were never asked to donate blood, ignorance, long distance from place of donation, time management, misconception and difficulty in transportation. Table-1 gives the division of two group i.e. donors of blood and non-donor of blood, a large quantity of the participants were from fifteen to thirty years of age.

Table-I: Distribution of sample into donors and non-donors according to age

Age group (Years)	15 - 30	30 - 45	45 - 60	> 60	Total
Donors	153.0	42.0	11.0	2.0	208.0
Non-donors	328.0	59.0	7.0	7.0	401.0
Total	481.0	101.0	18.0	9.0	609.0

The large quantity of the non donors was women and about seventy-six percent donators of blood were men. Table-2 shows that both groups are well qualified.

Sex	Men	Women	Total
Donors	185	23	208
Non-donors	150	251	401
Total	335	274	609

Table-3 provides about the ideas, faiths, behaviours and awareness about donation and transferring of blood. More than eighty-eight percent participants viewed that donation of blood was not a dangerous activity because preventive tests had carried out before start of donation of blood. More than eleven percent (majority were females) viewed that the donation of blood can cause any disease infection. More than six percent participants received blood one time in

their lives. Twenty percent refused from blood transfusion even if they would be in danger and in need of blood because it would lead to the infection. More than eighty-four percent participants gave their votes in favour of donation from direct donors. This would end up every risk of getting any disease. Forty-nine percent would get transfusion of blood from only close relatives.

Queries	Men		Women	
	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Is blood donation harmful to the donor?	28.0	307.0	42.0	232.0
Did you ever require blood transfusion?	14.0	321.0	24.0	250.0
Will you opt for blood transfusion in cases of emergency?	52.0	283.0	70.0	204.0
Would you like to know about the donor?	266.0	69.0	249.0	25.0
Are you willing to accept blood donations from strangers?	125.0	210.0	174.0	100.0
Did you noticed any other disease after transfusion?	28.0	307.0	43.0	231.0
Do u think that the blood provided in the blood banks is safe?	220.0	115.0	116.0	158.0
Do ytyou think that all types of surgery involve transfusion?	72.0	263.0	34.0	240.0

More than fifty-five percent samples were in favour of the storage and transfusion of blood from blood banks and other forty-four point five were against this. Process of transfusion of the blood caused AIDS and hepatitis in their close relation mentioned by eleven point six percent samples.

Most of the samples preferred to receive blood from females because in the population of Pakistan, females have fewer chances to get infected by any infectious disease than men. The blood was the requirement or not the requirement of the blood banks; about sixty-nine percent samples do not know this. This data is available in Table-4.

Table-IV: Level of knowledge regarding blood supply level at blood banks		
Gender	Response	Question: What is your idea about the available blood supply in the blood banks?
Males	Lees than needed	120
	More than needed	10
	Do not know	208
Females	Lees than needed	53
	More than needed	3
	Do not know	215

DISCUSSION:

The health planners of Pakistan are trying to maintain a safe and secure procedure for the supply of the blood. This issue cannot be underestimated due to a large amount of increased population and increase in the demand of blood. So, it is very important to interpret the ideas, behaviours, awareness and faiths of the people which are linked with the process of donation of blood and transfusion of blood from one person to another.

A large quantity of samples of this study were non-donors. The non-blood donors gave some reasons for not donating blood as they were never asked to donate blood, ignorance, long distance from place of donation, time management, misconception and difficulty in transportation. The studies done in the past also provide the same causes of not donating the blood [13, 16-22]. Thomson reported that eighty percent of the blood donors who are donating their blood for the very first time would never come back [23]. Misconceptions, different doubts and ignorance

are the different main hindrances in inhibiting donating blood. To wash out these types of fallacies from the minds of the people, seminars and different programs should be introduced.

Discrimination due to different race, age and sex are some other factors of inhibiting donation [25-27]. In this research, males' percentage of donors was greater than females' donors. Most of the non-donors were from fifteen to thirty years of age. So, motivation and education can kill this factor.

It is the duty of blood centres to make sure that it will not jeopardize the life of the donor. In this research, about eleven percent of samples believe that it is a dangerous activity. Sharma provided the same opinion in his four percent participants [28]. AIDS and hepatitis are the result of the blood donation in France as provided by Munoz [29].

About eighty-four percent of samples of this research work gave their vote in favour of direct donors

because it would terminate the danger of getting any dangerous infection. Forty-nine percent samples viewed that they would receive blood only from close relatives. According to Dingra, autologous donation is the best option to mitigate the concept of the infections [31].

Twenty percent samples were against the transfusion in every condition because of fear of getting any dangerous complication. Eleven point six percent samples gave data about their close relation who got AIDS and hepatitis from transfusion. Love discovered that a single donor of hepatitis C infected blood transfusion can affect a large number of the recipients [33].

Media programs and internet should be used for the awareness of the population about the processes of blood transfusion and blood donations. Such programs would encourage and motivate the persons to donate blood. It would make sure the availability of blood for every patient.

The populations should get awareness that the different types of the preventive tests carried out by the blood centre are the ways ensuring safety for both blood donors and blood recipients.

CONCLUSIONS

The mitigation of the wrong concepts about the donation of the blood & transfusion can achieve with proper education, eliminate the wrong thoughts about the clinics and increasing awareness.

REFERENCES:

1. Lowe KC, Ferguson E. Benefit and risk perceptions in transfusion medicine: Blood and blood substitutes. *J Intern Med* 2003;253:498-507.
2. Alam M, Masalmeh Bel D. Knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding blood donation among the Saudi population. *Saudi Med J* 2004;25(3):318-21.
3. Bashawri LA. Pattern of blood procurement, ordering and utilization in a University Hospital in Eastern Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J* 2002;23(5):555-61.
4. Domen RE. Paid versus volunteer blood donation in the United States historical review. *Transfus Med Rev* 1995;9:53-9.
5. Grham ID, Fergusson D, Dokainish H, Biggs J, NcAuley L, Laupacis A. Autologous versus allogeneic transfusion: patients' perceptions and experiences. *CMAJ* 1999;160:989-95.
6. Dietrich W, Busley R, Kriner M. Preoperative autologous blood donation in cardiac surgery:

- Reduction of allogeneic blood requirements. *Anaesthesist* 2006;55(7):753-9.
7. Randels MJ, Ferguson K, Strauss RG, Daniels M, Stehling L, Toy P. Preoperative autologous donation: Surgery clinic staff knowledge/attitudes. Preoperative Autologous Blood Donation Study Group. *J Clin Apher* 1994;9(3):168-70.
 8. Yoda M, Nonoyama M, Shimakura T. Autologous blood donation before elective off-pump coronary artery bypass grafting. *Surg Today* 2004;34(1):21-3.
 9. Mullar U, Roder C, Pisan M, Orlor R, El-Kerdi A, Egg. Autologous blood donation in total knee arthroplasty is not necessary. *Acta Orthop Scand* 2004;75(1):66-70.
 10. Moxey AJ, O'Connell DL, Treloar CJ, Han PY, Henry DA. Blood transfusion and autologous donation: A survey of post-surgical patients, interest group members and the public. *Transfus Med* 2005;15(1):19-32.
 11. Wake D, Cutting W. Blood transfusion in developing countries: Problems, priorities and practicalities. *Trop Doct* 1998;28:4-8.
 12. Gader AMA, Momen AK, Hashash AJ. King Saud University Donor Drive: a creative stimulus on the way to a Saudi National Blood transfusion Service. *Ann Saudi Med* 1988;8:403.
 13. Ferguson E, Farrell K, James V, Lowe KC. Trustworthiness of information about blood donation and transfusion in relation to knowledge and perceptions of risk: an analysis of UK stakeholder groups. *Transfus Med* 2004;14(3):205-16.
 14. Goodnough LT. Risk of blood transfusion. *Crit Care Med* 2003;31(12):S678-86.
 15. Herve P, Lapierre V, Morel P, Tiberghien P. What present strategies are helpful in improving transfusion safety in France. *Ann Med Interne* 1999;150(8):623-30.
 16. Olaiya MA, Alakiji W, Ajala A, Olatunji RO. Knowledge, attitude, beliefs and motivation toward blood donations among blood donor in Lagos. *Transfus Med* 2004;14(1):13-7.
 17. Fernandez MA, de Dios L, Castillo J, Lopez BA, Rodriguez FA. Attitudes, beliefs, and motivations in blood donors and non-donors. *Sangre (Barc)* 1996;41(6):413-6.
 18. Cacioppo JT, Gardner WL. What underlines medical donor attitudes and behavior? *Health Psychol* 1993;12(4):269-71.
 19. Hupfer ME, Taylor DW, Letwin JA. Understanding Canadian student motivations and beliefs about giving blood. *Transfusion* 2005;45(2):149-61.
 20. Oswalt R, Gordon J. Blood donor motivation: A

- survey of minority college students. *Psychol Rep* 1993;72(3 Pt 1):785-6.
21. Jacobs B, Berege ZA. Attitudes and beliefs about blood donation among adults in Mwanza Region, Tanzania. *East Afr Med J* 1995;72(6):345-8.
 22. Allen J, Butler DD. Assessing the effects of donor knowledge and perceived risk on intentions to donate blood. *J Health Care Mark* 1993;13(3):26-33.
 23. Thomson RA, Bethel J, Lo AY, Ownby HE, Nass CC, William AE. Retention of "safe" blood donor. The Retrovirus Epidemiology Donor Study. *Transfusion* 1998;38:359-67.
 24. Rajagopalan M, Pulimood R. Attitudes of medical and nursing students towards blood donation. *Natl Med J India* 1998;11(1):12-3.
 25. Boulware LE, Ratner LE, Cooper LA, Sosa JA, LaVeist TA, Powe NR. Understanding disparities in donor behavior: race and gender differences in willingness to donate blood and cadaveric organs. *Med Care* 2002;40(2):85-95.
 26. Burnett JJ, Leigh JH. Distinguishing characteristics of blood donor segments defined in terms of donation frequency. *J Health Care Mark* 1986; 6(2):38-48.
 27. Chliaoutakis J, Trakas DJ, Socrataki F, Lemonidou C, Papaioannou D. Blood donor behaviour in Greece: implications for health policy. *Soc Sci Med* 1994;38(10):1461-7.
 28. Sharma UK, Schreiber GB, Glynn SA, Nass CC, Higgins MJ, Tu Y, et al. Retrovirus Epidemiology Donor Study. Knowledge of HIV/AIDS transmission and screening in United States blood donors. *Transfusion* 2001;41(11):1341-50.
 29. Munoz Sastre MT, Bacq Y, Mullet E, Sorum PC. Misconceptions regarding hepatitis C in the French public. *Prev Med* 2002;34(6):596-9.
 30. Moltzan C, Proulx N, Bormanis J, Lander N, Degroot H, Rock G. Perceptions and motivations of Canadian autologous blood donors. *Transfus Med* 2001;11(3):177-82.
 31. Dhingra-Kumar N, Sikka M, Madan N, Sood SK. Evaluation of awareness and utilization of an autologous blood transfusion programme. *Transfus Med* 2001;11(3):177-82.
 32. Kingston ME, Harder EJ, Al-Jaberi MM, Bailey TM, Roberts GT, Sheth KV. Acquired immune deficiency syndrome in the Middle East from imported blood. *Transfusion* 1985;25(4):317-8.
 33. Love A, Molnegren V, Mansson AS, Smaradottir A, Thorsteinsson SB, Widell A. Evolution of hepatitis C virus variants following blood transfusion from one infected donor to several recipients: A long-term follow-up. *J Gen Virol* 2004;85:441-50.